

Some Molecular Adducts of Diphenyltellurium(IV)-bis-(trifluoroacetate) and -(trichloroacetate)

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Diphenyltellurium(IV) bis(trifluoroacetate) forms 1:1 molecular adducts with various N, O and S donor bases. The corresponding reactions with $(C_6H_5)_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$, however, appear to depend upon the nature of the bases. Thus, $(C_6H_5)_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$ gives 1:1 molecular adducts with diethylacetamide and morpholine, whereas 4-picoline, tetramethylpiperidine and dimethylacetamide afford adducts of the type $[(C_6H_5)_2TeCl_2 \cdot L]$. With 3-picoline-N-oxide and chloride ion, $[(C_6H_5)_2Te(CCl_3)_2 \cdot ONC_5H_4CH_3]$ and $[(C_6H_5)_2Te(CCl_3)_2 \cdot Cl]^-$, respectively, are obtained

RECENTLY, synthesis and characterisation of $R_2Te(OCOR')_2$ ($R' = CF_3, CCl_3, CHCl_2$ and CH_2Cl ; $R = Me, Ph, p-MeOC_6H_4$) have been reported¹. In continuation of our interest in the synthesis and reactivity of organotellurium(IV) compounds², we report herein the Lewis acid behaviour of $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ and $Ph_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$ towards some N, O, S donor bases and tetraalkylammonium salts.

Experimental

All manipulations were carried out under dry N_2 atmosphere. Ph_2TeCl_2 was prepared by the reported procedure³. $TeCl_4$ (B.D.H.) was used as such. $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ and $Ph_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$ were prepared as reported¹. The Lewis bases were procured from Alpha/Aldrich. The liquid ligands were distilled and the solids were recrystallised from suitable solvent before use. The solvents were purified and dried by standard methods. Physicochemical studies were made as described elsewhere¹.

Reactions with bases: The direct interaction of $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ with various Lewis bases (Table 1) yielded molecular adducts of 1:1 stoichiometry.

Reaction of $Ph_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$ under similar condition with Lewis bases, yielded product listed in Table 2. A typical preparation is described below.

To a solution of $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ (2.54 g, 5 mmol) in dichloromethane (~20 ml) was added an excess of tetramethylene sulphoxide (2.08 g, 20 mmol) in the same solvent (20 ml) and the mixture gently refluxed for ~4 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated and the molecular adduct was precipitated by the addition of dry petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). It was filtered, washed several times with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. Similarly, the reaction of $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ with $(C_2H_5)_4NCl$ was carried out using chloroform as a solvent.

Results and Discussion

All molecular adducts (Table 1) are sharp melting colourless solids soluble in common organic solvents except the anionic complexes. The reactions of Lewis bases with $Ph_2Te(OCOCF_3)_2$ and $Ph_2Te(OCOCCH_3)_2$ appear to follow equations (1) and (2); the results of equation (2) are presented in Table 2.

where, $L = O(CH_2)_4NH, CH_3CON(C_2H_5)_2$; $L' = H_3CC_5H_4NO, Me_4NCl$;

$L'' = Me_2C(CH_2)_8CMe_2NH, CH_3CON(CH_3)_2, 4-CH_3C_5H_4N, Bu_4NBr.$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR DATA OF $\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCOOF})_2 \cdot \text{L}$

Compd. L	M.p. °C	Te % : Found/ (Calcd.)	Ir band of OCO (cm^{-1})			Characteristic ir bands (cm^{-1})		
			$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO})$	$\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$	$-\Delta\nu(\text{OCO})^a$	Free base (ν_1)	adducts (ν_2)	($\nu_1 - \nu_2$)
$(\text{Me}_2\text{N})_2\text{CO}$	103	20.40 (20.45)	1 680	1 400	280	(C=O) 1 640	1 600	-40
$\text{CH}_3\text{N}(\text{OH}_2)_2\text{CO}$	80	20.43 (20.55)	1 690	1 410	280	(C=O) 1 620	1 605	-15
$(\text{OH}_2)_2\text{SO}$	110	20.70 (20.86)	1 690	1 405	285	(S=O) 1 020	995	-25
$[\text{Me}(\text{OH}_2)_2]_2\text{SO}$	160	18.96 (19.04)	1 700	1 407	293	(S=O) 1 057	1 040	-17
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH}_2)_2\text{SO}$	190	17.17 (17.29)	1 690	1 405	285	(S=O) 1 036	1 020	-16
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{PO}$	172	16.20 (16.24)	1 690	1 395	295	(P=O) 1 195	1 115	-80
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{PS}$	139	15.85 (15.91)	1 690	1 400	290	(P=S) 637	615	-22
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{AsO}$	162	15.23 (15.38)	1 685	1 395	290	(As=O) 880	865	-15
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH})_2\text{OS}$	164	17.26 (17.34)	1 685	1 383	302	(N-H) 3 210	3 300	+90
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N} : \text{CHNH}$	126	20.23 (20.39)	1 700	1 420	280	(C=N) 3 000	3 050	+50
$\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{OH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2\text{NH}$	172	19.60 (19.87)	1 680	1 390	290	(N-H) 3 380	3 050	-280
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}$	136	20.13 (20.23)	1 680	1 384	296	(N=O) 1 245	1 210	-36

^a ($-\Delta\nu(\text{OCO}) = \nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO}) - \nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$).

TABLE 2—REACTIVITY OF $\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OOCOCl})_2$ WITH SOME BASES

Ligand	Product	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)	
			Te	Cl
$\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{NH}$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OOCOCl})_2\text{NH}(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{O}]$	84	18.20 (18.99)	17.20 (17.55)
$\text{OH}_2\text{CON}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OOCOCl})_2\text{CH}_2\text{CON}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2]$	80	17.48 (17.68)	29.40 (29.51)
$\text{Me}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2\text{NH}$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{TeCl}_2\text{NHMe}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2]$	107	21.40 (21.48)	11.70 (11.95)
$4\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{N}$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{TeCl}_2\text{NC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2]$	160	28.40 (28.63)	15.80 (15.93)
$(\text{OH}_2)_2\text{COONCH}_3$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{TeCl}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CON}(\text{CH}_3)_2]$	59	28.72 (29.02)	15.88 (16.18)
Bu_4NBr	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{TeCl}_2\text{Br}][\text{Bu}_4\text{N}]^a$	57	18.80 (18.91)	22.12 (22.38)
$3\text{-CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}$	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCl})_2\text{ONC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2]$	65d	19.98 (20.12)	33.80 (33.48)
Me_2NOI	$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCl})_2\text{Cl}]\text{Me}_2\text{N}$	44d	17.60 (17.82)	34.16 (34.70)

^aCl+Br determined mixed.

The molar conductance values of 10^{-3} M solution of the adducts in nitrobenzene indicate non-electrolytic nature of the compounds. The complexes with tetraalkylammonium salts show 1:1 electrolytic behaviour⁴.

In the ir spectra of molecular adducts with O-donors (Table 1), the absorptions due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}^{5,6}$, $\nu_{\text{S=O}}^{7,8}$, $\nu_{\text{N=O}}^9$, $\nu_{\text{P=O}}^{10}$ and $\nu_{\text{As=O}}^{10}$ show distinct negative shifts as compared to the free ligands, indicating coordination from the oxygen atoms of the bases. In the adducts of phosphine sulphide and nitrogen donor bases, $\nu_{\text{P=S}}^{11}$, and $\nu_{\text{N-H}}^{12-14}$ or $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, respectively, are shifted to lower frequency

region indicating Te←S or Te←N bonding. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ values are found in the expected range for all the complexes (Table 1). Further, the $\Delta\nu_{\text{OCO}}$ of about 290 cm^{-1} is consistent with unidentately bonded CF_3COO groups. In the ir spectra of the adducts $\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{CCl}_3)_2 \cdot \text{L}$, absorptions due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ are absent whereas those due to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{CCl}_3)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{CCl}_3)$ appear at 830 and $690 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively¹⁵. The spectra of $\text{Ph}_2\text{TeCl}_2 \cdot \text{L}$ (2c) agree closely with similar known compounds.

¹H nmr spectra: The ¹H nmr spectra of a few representative complexes were recorded in CDCl_3

at 60 MHz. The pmr spectra of $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2(\text{Cl})]$ exhibit signals at δ 7.9 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(o)$), 7.36 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(m, p)$), 1.0–1.13 (12H, t, $4 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$) and 2.93–3.3 (8H, q, $4 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$). Each triplet further splits into 1 : 1 (approx.) triplets, which may be due to coupling with ^{14}N nucleus¹⁶. The pmr spectra of $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2\text{OC}$

$(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{NCH}_3]$ display signals at δ 7.6 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(o)$), 7.4 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(m, p)$), 2.2 (2H, br, t, CH_2), 1.66 and 1.70 (4H, s, $\text{C}-\text{CH}_2$). The pmr spectra of

$[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2\text{NH CMe}_2(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2]$ exhibit signals at δ 7.75 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(o)$), 7.38 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(m, p)$), 1.26 (12H, s, CH_3-C) and 1.56 (6H, s, CH_2-C). The

pmr spectra of $[\text{Ph}_2\text{Te}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{NH}]$

display δ 7.83 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(o)$), 7.1 (m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5(m, p)$), 3.8 (4H, m, CH_2-O) and 3.1 (4H, m, CH_2-N). The $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2$ and $\text{O}-\text{CH}_2$ resonances on complexation, get broadened and shift to lower field in comparison to free morpholine (δ 2.57 ($\text{N}-\text{CH}_2-$) and 3.34 ($\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-$)). The signal due to NH proton perhaps also broadens and shifts upfield relative to the free base (δ 2.07 (NH)), and is not observed in the spectrum.

The complexes may be considered to be pseudo-octahedral having the following structure,

X = Cl, CCl_2 , OCOCF_3 , or OCOCOC_2 .

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